

A first look at the non-acarine arachnid biodiversity of the Meerkat National Park, South Africa

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ABSTRACT: In this study, we present the first preliminary checklist of the non-acarine arachnids of the Meerkat National Park, based on iNaturalist images generated during a BioBlitz conducted in the park in October 2024 and an Entomology field excursion conducted by the University of the Free State in March - April 2025 in the Jaskloof area. During the latter, sampling was conducted in three biotopes (open Nama Karoo grassland, a rocky hillside and riparian woodland) using a standardized sampling protocol (beating, sweeping and pitfalls), supplemented by ad hoc collecting by beating, hand collecting from rocks, litter sifting and night collecting. A total of 89 spider species in 30 families were recorded, as well as six species of scorpions, four species of solifuges and two species of pseudoscorpions. The most species-rich families sampled were Salticidae (15 spp.) and Gnaphosidae (14 spp.). We also generated 33 DNA barcodes representing 22 species based on the material collected, all of which are imaged. All of the species identified to species level (60 spp.) can be considered of Least Concern. The majority of them are southern African endemics (31 spp.), whereas 10 are South African endemics, 13 Afrotropical endemics and six species are cosmopolitan. Although this is only a preliminary survey carried out in a small portion in the west of the park, it provides valuable baseline data to guide future sampling efforts and species identifications.

INTRODUCTION

The South African National Survey of Arachnida (SANSa) has made a massive effort during the last three decades to improve sample coverage of non-acarine arachnids in the country, with a particular focus on identifying gaps in sampling effort and addressing them through targeted sampling (Foord *et al.*, 2011; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2015). This effort, largely driven by the development and application of the standardized SANSa rapid sampling protocol (Haddad & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2015), was largely focused in the eastern and central parts of the country, while the arid and semi-arid western half remained poorly sampled (Janion-Scheepers *et al.*, 2016; Foord *et al.*, 2020; Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023; Van der Mescht *et al.*, 2024), a situation that continues to persist.

One of the specific aims of SANSa was to sample and provide baseline data on the South African National Parks (SANParks, #DIPSA 1296). Although a few parks were well sampled and the results published prior to the completion of SANSa phases I and II, most of the 19 parks did not have a comprehensive checklist of the non-acarine arachnid fauna until recently (see Haddad *et al.*, 2025). Despite this progress, several parks remain undersampled and two, Meerkat and Camdeboo, have no spider records at all. Considering the significance of SANParks to conservation in South Africa, it is essential that data be generated for those parks for which no checklists are available.

During March-April 2025, the 3rd year Entomology students at the University of the Free State (UFS) undertook the annual student field excursion to the previously unsampled Meerkat National Park (MNP) near Carnarvon in the karoo. MNP is South Africa's most recently proclaimed national park (March 2020), which was an effort to offset the impact of the Square Kilometer Array (SKA) telescope system on the environment. Initially, a Bioblitz in the MNP was held in October 2024 but could not be attended by the authors, which resulted in the excursion being held there to facilitate sampling of non-acarine arachnids. The primary objective was to provide baseline biodiversity data on arthropods, focusing on insects and non-acarine arachnids.

MATERIAL AND METHODS

The study was undertaken in the MNP in the Upper Karoo and Bushmanland area, with the nearest towns being Carnarvon, Williston, Sakrivier, Brandvlei and Vanwyksvlei. Topographically, the region is characterized by continuous and isolated flat-topped mesas separated by open plains. The area experiences cold winters and very hot summers, with most of the rainfall falling during late summer. For more details of the MNP geology and vegetation, see Van Rooyen & Van Rooyen (2022).

To effectively sample arthropods, a variety of sampling methods are required to collect in different habitat strata. This not only allows for better characterization of assemblages occupying different microhabitats within each biotope but enables comparisons between strata within a biotope and within-stratum differences between biotopes (as presented in the student reports). The UFS Entomology students were divided into three groups that replicated a rapid sampling protocol (Haddad, 2021) in the three biotopes sampled, an open Nama Karoo grassland (Fig. 1A), a riparian woodland (Fig. 1B) and a northwest-facing rocky hillside (Fig. 1C), all in the Jaskloof area along the western margin of the MNP. However, leaf litter was sparse in two of the three biotopes, so litter sifting was replaced with sweep-netting as a sampling method. Due to logistical constraints, no sampling could be conducted in the eastern section of the park in the proximity of the SKA, which is dominated by open gravel plains (Fig. 1D).

Each group took 10 samples of vegetation beating (50 beats each), 10 pitfall traps left out for four days, and 10 samples of sweep-netting vegetation (50 sweeps each), which was replicated in each of the three biotopes. Additional collecting was conducted by the authors by beating, hand collecting under rocks, leaf litter sifting and night collecting around Jaskloof (Fig. 1E-F). We also set up a light trap for the students to collect nocturnal insects on four of the nights, where any visiting arachnids were collected. C.H. sorted and identified all the spiders and other arachnids for the students so that the data could be included in their reports. Material has been deposited in the National Museum in Bloemfontein (spiders and pseudoscorpions), American Museum of Natural History in New York (scorpions) and Ditsong National Museum of Natural History in Pretoria (solifuges).

Figure 1. Biotopes in the Meerkat National Park. A Open plain with Nama Karoo grassland, Jaskloof; B Northwest-facing hillside, Jaskloof; C Hillside and riparian woodland, Jaskloof; D Open gravel plain near park entrance, with the SKA in the background; E Jaskloof farmhouse and outbuildings, with hillsides and riparian woodland; F Farm dam at Jaskloof. Photos: A N. Zulu; B –F C. Haddad.

In addition, DNA barcodes (cytochrome *c* oxidase subunit I, COI) were generated for 33 spider specimens from the park (Appendix 1). The plates were submitted to the Canadian Centre for DNA Barcoding and all sequence data is publicly accessible on the SPIZA project on BOLD (www.boldsystems.org). Some of the arthropods collected were photographed by Ruan Booysen and Rudolph Steenkamp and the images and data have been uploaded to iNaturalist, to supplement images taken during the Bioblitz in October 2024.

For each species in the checklist (Appendix 1), we present an indication of the Red List conservation status (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023). The species sampled were all considered Least Concern (LC), except for those only identified to genus level, which were not evaluated (NE); no species belonged to any of the threat categories. The endemicity index was also provided for each species, including the following applicable categories: SAE – South African endemic; STHE – Southern African endemic (south of Zambezi and Kunene Rivers); AE – endemic to the Afrotropical Region; C – cosmopolitan.

RESULTS

Altogether, 89 spider species in 30 families were collected, together with six species of scorpions, four species of solifuges and two species of pseudoscorpions (Appendix 1). Of these, seven species were recorded during the BioBlitz of October 2024 and are known from photographic records on iNaturalist only; the remaining species were collected from voucher specimens during surveys in March 2025, although some were previously also recorded on iNaturalist or added following the survey (Appendix 1).

Images of some of the commonly collected species are presented in Fig. 2. *Thysanina gracilis* (Trachelidae, Fig. 2A), juveniles of an unidentified *Dendryphantas* sp. (Salticidae, Fig. 2H) and various Philodromidae and Oxyopidae were abundant in beating samples in all three biotopes. Species commonly collected from under rocks on the hillsides and in the riparian woodland included *Ibala bilinearis* (Gnaphosidae, Fig. 2B), a new *Pseudauximus* sp. (Macrobonidae, Fig. 2C), a new *Scytodes* sp. (Scytodidae, Fig. 2D), *Prodidomus purpurascens* (Prodidomidae, Fig. 2E), a likely new *Quamtana* sp. (Pholcidae) and a new *Euophrys* sp. (Salticidae, Fig. 2J). Only a single *Hexophthalma hahni* (Sicariidae, Fig. 2F) adult female and juvenile *Harpactira* sp. (Theraphosidae, Fig. 2I) were collected under rocks around the Jaskloof residence. Common in sweep-netting samples were *Argiope australis* (Araneidae) in the open plain and various Philodromidae in all three biotopes.

Paradonea variegata (Eresidae, Fig. 2G) males were active on the soils surface in the late afternoon, whereas females were collected from their cribellate retreat-webs constructed beneath large rocks in the riparian woodland, open plains and hillsides, particularly around the Jaskloof homestead. Males of this species mimic *Camponotus fulvopilosus* ants, which are common in the park. Two myrmecophilous species, *Mexcala rufa* (Salticidae) and *Stiphropus affinis* (Thomisidae, Fig. 2K) were commonly found around *C. fulvopilosus* nests near Jaskloof and are likely widespread in the park. Although the new *Cydrela* sp. (Zodariidae) also clearly has similar colouration to *C. fulvopilosus*, it was only collected in pitfall traps.

The rapid sampling protocol used was relatively ineffective in sampling large numbers of spiders, and both numbers and species richness per sample were markedly lower than when the protocol was used in the western Free State, in the transition zone between the Nama Karoo and Grassland biomes (Haddad, 2021). Generally, beating sampled the highest abundance and species richness in all

three biotopes, although the hillside consistently performed poorest for both metrics for all three methods used. Often, only one or two spiders were collected per sample, explaining why the abundance and species richness per sample were very similar at all biotope-method combinations (Fig. 3).

The 33 specimens submitted for DNA barcoding represent 22 species (Appendix 1; Fig. 4). This includes the first DNA barcodes in the SPIZA project for *Caponia spiralifera*, *Camillina pavesii*, *Setaphis browni*, *Pseudauximus* sp.*, *Theuma schreineri*, *Helafricanus* sp.*, *Euophrys* sp.*, *Stiphropus affinis* and *Caesetius* sp.* (* indicates new species).

DISCUSSION

Through our efforts, we were able to generate a meaningful baseline dataset on non-acarine biodiversity in the MNP, which will hopefully stimulate research there in the future. As this was only a preliminary biodiversity assessment with very limited geographical scope in the park and only carried out over the course of one week, it would be premature to make any management recommendations. Nonetheless, valuable data has been provided to facilitate future ecological and conservation work in the park.

It is worth mentioning that several new taxa were collected during our study, including species of *Ammoxenus* (Gnaphosidae), *Pseudauximus*, *Euophrys* and *Helafricanus*, *Scytodes* and *Caesetius*, as well as a likely new species of the insect order Mantophasmatodea. Further new species may belong to taxonomically poorly studied spider families that could only be identified to genus level. For the orders Solifugae and Pseudoscorpiones, specialist identifications following more detailed study are necessary to confirm the identity of the species sampled. For example, only female solifuges were sampled for two species, and males are required for accurate species identification based on the flagellum structure. Four species of solifuges have been recorded from the Carnarvon area (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.* 2006), which may help narrow down the species likely to occur in the MNP.

During a relatively short period of one week, we were able to generate a sizable dataset on the arthropods occurring in the vicinity of Jaskloof. Although this was only baseline biodiversity survey, it has enabled us to familiarize ourselves with the landscape and facilities in the park and to generate a lot of material that will be valuable for taxonomic study, studies of predation biology and DNA barcoding. We hope to visit again in the future and explore the area and its biodiversity further.

All the species identified to species level are considered Least Concern according to their current South African Spider Red List scores (Dippenaar-Schoeman *et al.*, 2023). In evaluating the global distribution of all the species sampled, six are cosmopolitan, 13 have a broad distribution in the Afrotropical Region and 10 are South African endemics. The majority of species identified to species level are southern African endemics (31 spp.), usually with distributions extending into Namibia and sometimes other southern African countries. A further 41 species could only be identified to genus level and would need to be evaluated once they are (re)described or adult specimens have been collected. It is plausible that some of them may be of conservation concern.

The MNP remains largely unexplored with regards to its arthropod biodiversity, with most of the park aside from Jaskloof never having been sampled before. Future efforts to collect in other areas could be facilitated by the upgrade of the old farmhouses and other accommodation sources, which will improve accessibility and logistics. We look forward to the proposed changes and having the possibility to sample this unique Nama Karoo landscape again in the future and provide data on the arthropod fauna.

Figure 2. Habitus photographs of several live Arachnida collected in the Meerkat National Park: A *Thysanina gracilis* (Trachelidae); B *Ibala bilinearis* (Gnaphosidae); C *Pseudauximus* sp. (Macrobnidae); D *Scytodes* sp. (Scytodidae); E *Prodidomus purpurascens* (Prodidomidae); F *Hexophthalma hahni* (Sicariidae); G *Paradonea variegata* (Eresidae); H *Dendryphantes* sp. (Salticidae); I *Harpactira* sp. (Theraphosidae); J *Euophrys* sp. (Salticidae); K *Stiphropus affinis* (Thomisidae); L *Faella* sp. (Feaellidae); M *Nanolpium* sp. (Hesperolpiidae); N *Uroplectes gracilior* (Buthidae); O *Parabuthus schlechteri* (Buthidae); P *Opisthophthalmus karrooensis* (Scorpionidae); Q *Karasbergia methueni* (Buthidae); R *Blossia* sp. (Daesiidae). Photos: R. Booysen.

Figure 3. Mean \pm SD of spider abundance (A) and species richness (B) per sample collected by student groups in the Meerkat National Park. Abbreviations: NK – Nama Karoo veld; HI – Hillside; RW – Riparian woodland; B – beating vegetation; S – sweep-netting vegetation; P – pitfalls.

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Figure 4. Spider species from Meerkat National Park submitted for DNA barcoding: A *Caponia spiralifera*, male (Caponiidae); B, C *Paradonea variegata*, male (B) and female (C) (Eresidae); D *Camillina pavesii*, male (Gnaphosidae); E *Ibala bilinearis*, female (Gnaphosidae); F *Setaphis browni*, female (Gnaphosidae); G *Pseudauximus* sp., male (Macrobunidae); H *Diaphorocellus biplagiatus*, male (Palpimanidae); I, J *Palpimanus* sp., female (I) and male (J) (Palpimanidae); K, L *Prodidomus purpurascens*, male (K) and female (L) (Prodidomidae); M *Theuma schreineri*, female (Prodidomidae); N, O *Philodromus otjimbembe*, male (N) and female (O) (Philodromidae); P, Q *Euophrys* sp., male (P) and female (Q) (Salticidae); R *Helafricanus prozysniskii*, female (Salticidae); S *H. trepidus*, male; T, U *Helafricanus* sp., male (T) and female (U); V *Evarcha villosa*, male (Salticidae); W *Hexophthalma hahni*, female (Sicariidae); X, Y *Stiphropus affinis*, male (X) and female (Y) (Thomisidae); Z *Xysticus sagittifer*, female (Thomisidae); AA–CC *Thysanina gracilis*, males (Trachelidae), showing variation in cheliceral length; DD *Afrocefto africana*, female (Trachelidae); EE, FF *Caesetius* sp., males (Zodariidae). Photos: C. Haddad.

Appendix 1. List of the non-acarine arachnids recorded from the Meerkat National Park, South Africa. Asterisks indicate new species. Abbreviations: Con – conservation status; End – endemism; NK – Nama Karoo grassland; HI – hillside; RW – riparian woodland; Barc – species submitted for DNA barcoding (cytochrome c oxidase subunit I); iNat – iNaturalist record. Conservation status: LC – Least Concern; NE – Not Evaluated. Endemicity index: AE – endemic to the Afrotropical Region; C – cosmopolitan; SAE – South African endemic; STHE – Southern African endemic (south of Zambezi and Kunene Rivers).

Family	Species	Con	End	NK	HI	RW	Barc	iNat
ARANEAE								
Agelenidae	sp. indet.	NE	–					X
Araneidae	<i>Argiope australis</i> (Walckenaer, 1805)	LC	AE	X	X	X		X
	<i>Larinioides</i> sp.	NE	–			X		
	<i>Neoscona subfusca</i> (C.L. Koch, 1837)	LC	C	X		X		
Caponiidae	<i>Caponia spiralis</i> Purcell, 1904	LC	SAE		X		X	
Cheiracanthiidae	<i>Cheiramiona</i> sp.	NE	–	X	X	X		X
Eresidae	<i>Gandanameno</i> sp.	NE	–					X
	<i>Paradonea variegata</i> (Purcell, 1904)	LC	STHE		X		X	X
	<i>Stegodyphus dumicola</i> Pocock, 1898	LC	STHE					X
	<i>Stegodyphus tentoriicola</i> Purcell, 1904	LC	STHE	X				X
Gnaphosidae	<i>Ammoxenus coccineus</i> Simon, 1893	LC	STHE	X				
	<i>Ammoxenus</i> sp.*	NE	–		X			
	<i>Asemesthes albobittatus</i> Purcell, 1908	LC	STHE	X		X		
	<i>Asemesthes reflexus</i> Tucker, 1923	LC	SAE	X		X		
	<i>Camillina pavesii</i> (Simon, 1897)	LC	AE		X		X	
	<i>Camillina</i> sp. 2	NE	–			X		
	<i>Ibala bilinearis</i> (Tucker, 1923)	LC	STHE	X	X		X	X
	<i>Micaria</i> sp.	NE	–					X
	<i>Setaphis browni</i> (Tucker, 1923)	LC	C		X			
	<i>Xerophaeus</i> sp.	NE	–		X			X
	<i>Zelotes fuliginus</i> (Purcell, 1907)	LC	AE			X		
	<i>Zelotes lavus</i> Tucker, 1923	LC	STHE			X		
	<i>Zelotes scrutatus</i> (O.P.-Cambridge, 1872)	LC	AE			X		
Hersiliidae	<i>Tyrotama</i> sp.	NE	–		X			X
Linyphiidae	<i>Metaleptyphantes</i> sp.	NE	–	X		X		
	<i>Pelecopsis janus</i> Jocqué, 1984	LC	STHE	X	X	X		
	<i>Pelecopsis</i> sp. 2	NE	–		X			
	sp. indet.	NE	–			X		
Liocranidae	<i>Rhaeboctesis</i> sp. imm.	NE	–		X			X
Lycosidae	<i>Arctosa promontorii</i> (Purcell, 1900)	LC	SAE		X	X		
	<i>Evippomma squamulatum</i> (Simon, 1898)	LC	STHE		X			
	<i>Hogna</i> sp.	NE	–			X		X
	<i>Proevippa</i> sp.	NE	–		X	X		X
Macrobnidae	<i>Pseudauximus</i> sp.*	NE	–		X		X	X
Oecobiidae	<i>Oecobius putus</i> O. P.-Cambridge, 1876	LC	C		X			X
Oxyopidae	<i>Oxyopes bothai</i> Lessert, 1915	LC	AE	X	X	X		X
	<i>Oxyopes</i> sp. 2	NE	–	X				X
	<i>Peucetia striata</i> Karsch, 1878	LC	AE		X			
	<i>Peucetia transvaalica</i> Simon, 1896	LC	AE			X		X
	<i>Peucetia transvaalica</i> Simon, 1896	LC	AE			X		X
Palpimanidae	<i>Diaphorocellus biplagiatus</i> Simon, 1893	LC	STHE		X	X	X	X
	<i>Palpimanus</i> sp.	NE	–		X		X	X
Philodromidae	<i>Hirriusa arenacea</i> (Lawrence, 1927)	LC	STHE	X				
	<i>Philodromus grosi</i> Lessert, 1943	LC	AE		X	X		
	<i>Philodromus otjimbumbé</i> Lawrence, 1927	LC	STHE	X	X	X	X	
	<i>Philodromus</i> sp. 3	NE	–	X			X	
	<i>Thanatus vulgaris</i> Simon, 1870	LC	C			X		

Family	Species	Con	End	NK	HI	RW	Barc	iNat
Pholcidae	<i>Quamtana</i> sp.*	NE	–			X		
	<i>Smeringopus sederberg</i> Huber, 2012	LC	SAE		X	X		
Pisauridae	<i>Rothus aethiopicus</i> (Pavesi, 1883)	LC	AE	X		X		X
Prodidomidae	<i>Prodidomus purpurascens</i> Purcell, 1904	LC	SAE		X	X	X	X
	<i>Theuma schreineri</i> Purcell, 1907	LC	STHE	X				
	<i>Theuma</i> sp. 2	NE	–			X		
Salticidae	<i>Dendryphantas</i> sp. imm.	NE	–			X		X
	<i>Euophrys</i> sp.*	NE	–		X	X	X	X
	<i>Evarcha karas</i> Wesolowska, 2011	LC	STHE			X		
	<i>Evarcha villosa</i> Wesolowska & Haddad, 2018	LC	SAE			X	X	
	<i>Helafricanus prozysinskii</i> (Wesolowska, 2003)	LC	STHE			X	X	
	<i>Helafricanus trepidus</i> (Simon, 1910)	LC	STHE			X	X	
	<i>Helafricanus</i> sp.*	NE	–			X	X	
	<i>Icius insolitus</i> (Wesolowska, 1999)	LC	STHE	X	X	X		X
	<i>Langona hirsuta</i> Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011	LC	SAE			X		
	<i>Mexcala rufa</i> Peckham & Peckham, 1902	LC	STHE		X	X		X
	<i>Pellenes geniculatus</i> (Simon, 1868)	LC	C			X		
	<i>Pellenes tharinae</i> Wesolowska, 2006	LC	STHE	X				
	<i>Phlegra karoo</i> Wesolowska, 2006	LC	STHE		X	X		
	<i>Psenec dependens</i> (Haddad & Wesolowska, 2011)	LC	SAE	X				
	<i>Thyene inflata</i> (Gerstäcker, 1873)	LC	AE	X		X		
Scytodidae	<i>Scytodes</i> sp.*	NE	–		X			X
Segestriidae	<i>Ariadna</i> sp.	NE	–		X			
Selenopidae	<i>Anyphops</i> sp. imm.	NE	–		X	X		X
Sicariidae	<i>Hexophthalma hahni</i> (Karsch, 1878)	LC	STHE			X	X	X
Sparassidae	<i>Olios correvoni</i> Lessert, 1921	LC	AE			X		
Tetragnathidae	<i>Tetragnatha</i> sp.	NE	–			X		
Theraphosidae	<i>Harpactira</i> sp.	NE	–			X		X
Theridiidae	<i>Achaearanea</i> sp.	NE	–			X		
	<i>Chryso</i> sp. imm.	NE	–			X		X
	<i>Latrodectus geometricus</i> C.L. Koch, 1841	LC	C			X		X
	<i>Steatoda</i> sp. imm.	NE	–			X		X
	<i>Theridion</i> sp.	NE	–			X		
Thomisidae	<i>Ansiae</i> sp.	NE	–	X	X			
	<i>Heriaeus zanii</i> Van Niekerk & Dippenaar-Schoeman, 2013	LC	SAE		X	X		X
	<i>Misumenops rubrodecoratus</i> Millot, 1942	LC	AE	X				
	<i>Stiphropus affinis</i> Lessert, 1923	LC	STHE		X	X	X	X
	<i>Thomisus stenningi</i> Pocock, 1900	LC	AE			X		X
	<i>Thomisus</i> sp. 2	NE	–			X		
	<i>Xysticus sagittifer</i> Lawrence, 1927	LC	STHE		X		X	
Trachelidae	<i>Afroceto africana</i> (Simon, 1910)	LC	STHE	X			X	
	<i>Thysanina gracilis</i> Lyle & Haddad, 2006	LC	STHE	X	X	X	X	
Zodariidae	<i>Caesetius</i> sp.*	NE	–	X			X	
SCORPIONES								
Buthidae	<i>Karasbergia methueni</i> Hewitt, 1913	LC	STHE	X	X	X		X
	<i>Parabuthus capensis</i> (Ehrenberg, 1831)	LC	STHE					X
	<i>Parabuthus schlechteri</i> Purcell, 1899	LC	STHE	X				X
	<i>Uroplectes gracilior</i> Hewitt, 1914	LC	STHE	X	X	X		X

Family	Species	Con	End	NK	HI	RW	Barc	iNat
Scorpionidae	<i>Opisthophthalmus carinatus</i> (Peters, 1861)	LC	STHE					X
	<i>Opisthophthalmus karrooensis</i> Purcell, 1898	LC	SAE	X	X			X
PSEUDOSCORPIONES								
Feaellidae	<i>Feaella</i> sp.	NE	–					
Hesperolpiidae	<i>Nanolpium</i> sp.	NE	–		X			X
					X	X		X
SOLIFUGAE								
Daesiidae	<i>Biton</i> sp.	NE	–					
	<i>Blossia</i> sp.	NE	–	X				X
Solpugidae	<i>Solpugiba lineata</i> (C. L. Koch, 1842)	LC	STHE	X				X
	<i>Zeriassa</i> sp.	NE	–			X		X
								X